

Architected Synthesis of a NMC core/shell cathode: Tailoring microstructure with tungsten oxide barrier for improved stability of Lithium-ion batteries

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Benefits and Obstacles of Ni-rich Cathodes in LiBs

- + High energy density
- + Increased storage capacity
- + Contribution to the circular economy (durability, recyclability and possibility of second life)

- Thermal stability
- Insufficient cycle life
- Nickel oxidation
- Capacitance reduction

Development of Core/shell-structured NMC Cathode Powders for sustainable LiBs with longer cycle life

Oxalate assisted co-precipitation method for synthesis

1. Dissolving Ni-, Mn-, and Co-acetates in water in the NMC90 proportion
2. Adding oxalic acid as a co-precipitation agent
3. Drying and calcinating at 850°C
4. Dissolving ammonium tungstate in isopropanol, adding NMC90 core, drying, and calcinating at 650 °C
5. Repeating steps 1–3 to prepare shell-solution in the NMC622 proportion
6. For shell coating, adding NMC90 core to the shell solution after the step 1 as an extra step

Microstructural characterization of calcined powder

Electrochemical performance characterization

- **Coin cell assembly:** Glass fiber separators, NMC cathode, lithium anode, and 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DMC (50/50 v/v); tested at C/10 rate
- **Lab-NMC622** shows higher C_{sp} than commercial NMC622

- **Core/shell** structure achieves ~125 mAh/g, with WO₃ coating ~135 mAh/g
- **650 °C annealed core/shell** shows highest cycling stability
- **NMC90** has a lower C_{sp} (~80 mAh/g) compared to shell NMC622

